

UV-Vis Spectral Changes in the Binding of Acyclic Diamines with a Zinc Porphyrin Tweezer†

XUEFEI HUANG, BABAK BORHAN, NINA BEROVA and KOJI NAKANISHI*

Department of Chemistry, Columbia University, New York City, NY, 10027, U.S.A.

Manuscript received 18 August 1998

Porphyrin tweezer 1 forms 1 : 1 complexes with a series of acyclic aliphatic α,ω -diamines. Chain elongation of the diamines is accompanied by a red-shift in UV-vis maxima and increase in half band-widths of the Soret bands. These changes are accounted for, respectively, by a decrease in exciton coupling and an increase in structural flexibility.

Porphyrins have been widely used in the studies of π - π interactions, photosynthetic mimics, and molecular recognition¹⁻⁴. Because of the ease in synthetic manipulation of peripheral functional groups, the intense Soret band ($\epsilon \sim 400000$ around 418 nm for tetra-arylporphyrins), and the availability of porphyrins incorporating a number of central metal atoms, porphyrin hosts linked by one or more bridges have been widely utilized in recognition of diamines, amino acids, carbohydrate, etc⁵⁻¹². Our own interest in porphyrins originated from its use as a chromophoric host for amines¹³, as well as their highly desirable chromophoric properties for use in exciton coupled circular dichroic spectroscopy¹⁴⁻¹⁷.

We have recently synthesized zinc porphyrin tweezer 1, i.e. a bisporphyrin connected by a pentanediol linker, and have found that it is capable of binding to acyclic chiral α,ω -diamines such as L-lysine methyl ester through zinc-nitrogen coordination to yield macrocyclic complexes (Fig. 1). Importantly, these complexes give rise to exciton coupled CD due to the chiral disposition between the two porphyrins, the couplet signs of which reflect the absolute configuration at C-2 of the chiral diamine¹³. In the following, the binding between the bisporphyrin host and a series of acyclic achiral α,ω -diamine guests $H_2N(CH_2)_nNH_2$ ($n = 2-10,12$, compounds 2-11) has been investigated by UV-vis in order to

clarify the relation between the host and the chain-length of guest molecules. This has led to the finding that (i) an increase in the diamine chain-length is accompanied by a red-shift in the λ_{max} of guest/host complex and a broadening of the Soret band, and (ii) host 1 is capable of binding to guests of various chain-lengths (n from 2 to 12) without much difference in binding constants.

UV-vis has been extensively used for monitoring the binding of zinc porphyrins with amines^{7,11,18,19}. Upon binding, characteristic red-shift of the zinc porphyrin Soret band occurs. For example, addition of primary monoamines such as isopropylamine (12) to tweezer 1 red-shifts the Soret band by 544 cm^{-1} (10 nm) from 23870 cm^{-1} (419 nm) of the empty tweezer 1 to 23326 cm^{-1} (429 nm) (Table 1). In the case of diamines 2-11, the bathochromic shifts of the Soret bands are dependent on the length of the guests (Table 1). Thus with diamine 2 ($n = 2$) the ν_{max} is shifted only 225 cm^{-1} from 23870 to 23645 cm^{-1} , whereas with increasing chain-length it is red-shifted in an almost linear manner so that with 11 ($n = 12$), the ν_{max} is shifted by 509 cm^{-1} to 23361 cm^{-1} (Fig. 2). The small bathochromic shifts observed in the complexes with short chains can be explained by exciton coupling theory, which predicts a blue-shift when the two chromophores are spatially disposed face to face parallel to each other²⁰⁻²².

Fig. 1. Structure of porphyrin tweezer 1 and proposed structure of 1 binding with diamines.

†Dedicated to Professor Sukh Dev on the occasion of his 75th. birth anniversary.

Fig. 2. Plot of ν_{\max} vs n (the number of methylene in the diamines). The solid line is the linear curve fit with $R = 0.982$.

TABLE 1—MAXIMA AND HALF BAND-WIDTH ($W_{1/2}$) OF THE SORET BANDS OF PORPHYRIN TWEEZER 1 BINDING WITH VARIOUS AMINES

	ν_{\max} cm^{-1}	$\Delta\nu^b$ cm^{-1}	λ_{\max} nm	$W_{1/2}$ cm^{-1}
No amines	23870	0	418.9	698
$n=2$ (2) ^a	23645	225	422.9	453
$n=3$ (3) ^a	23611	259	423.5	498
$n=4$ (4) ^a	23554	316	424.6	502
$n=5$ (5) ^a	23533	337	424.9	536
$n=6$ (6) ^a	23486	384	425.8	583
$n=7$ (7) ^a	23465	405	426.2	606
$n=8$ (8) ^a	23426	444	426.9	622
$n=9$ (9) ^a	23420	450	427.0	640
$n=10$ (10) ^a	23397	473	427.4	644
$n=12$ (11) ^a	23361	509	428.1	646
Isopropylamine (12)	23326	544	428.7	578

^a n denotes the number of methylene in diamine $\text{H}_2\text{N}(\text{CH}_2)_n\text{NH}_2$.

^b $\Delta\nu = \nu_{\max}(\text{no amines}) - \nu_{\max}(\text{with amine})$.

This parallel no-offset orientation of the two porphyrin rings in the host/diamine complexes is corroborated by ^1H nmr (Fig. 3). The close similarity in the ^1H nmr of the complex between zinc 5-(*p*-methylcarboxyphenyl)-10,15,20-triphenylporphyrin (13) and isopropylamine 12 (Fig. 3a) and that of tweezer 1 and isopropylamine 12 (Fig. 3b) shows that the orientation between two porphyrins in the 1/12 complex is random. However, in the nmr of the 1/2 complex, all pyrrole protons are shifted 0.3 ppm upfield to around 8.5 ppm (Fig. 3d). Significant upfield shifts of 0.4 ppm were observed for all the phenyl *ortho*-protons; the *meta*- and *para*-protons were also shifted upfield although to a smaller extent because they are more remote from the porphyrin ring. No downfield shift in the aromatic protons of the complex was seen. The presence of upfield shift coupled with the absence of any downfield shift in the aromatic protons indicates that the two porphyrins are held parallel to each other with no offset in the plane of the π -systems. This orientation is corroborated by our previous observations^{16,17} and the results by Hunter *et al.*⁷, i.e. lack of the offset parallel orientation led to upfield shift of the aromatic protons, while in offset spatial dispositions, both upfield and downfield shifts of the aromatic protons were observed. With longer diamines such as 7, ^1H nmr of the complex also showed similar trends as with the 1/2 complex but with smaller upfield shifts of all aromatic protons (Fig. 3c). This is presumably due to larger distance between the two porphyrins in the 1/7 complex. The smaller blue-shift of the Soret band of the 1/7 complex compared to the 1/2 complex can also be explained by the larger distance between the two porphyrins since a large distance leads to weaker exciton coup-

Fig. 3. ^1H nmr spectra of the aromatic regions in CDCl_3 of a) zinc 5-(*p*-methylcarboxyphenyl)-10,15,20-triphenylporphyrin (13) complex with 12, b) 1/12 complex, c) 1/7 complex, d) 1/2 complex.

Fig. 4. a) Plot of $W_{1/2}$ (cm^{-1}) vs n (number of methylene in the diamine), b) Schematic illustration of comparison between $W_{1/2}$ of the Soret band of rigid and flexible host and guests complexes.

ling and hence smaller blue-shift. The linearity seen in the ν_{max} red-shift with n results from the combined effect of changes in geometry of the host/guest complex.

The half band-width of the Soret bands of host/guest complexes also showed an interesting trend: larger the n , broader the Soret band (Table 1). As shown in Fig. 4a, with $n = 2$ (2) the Soret band is the sharpest, while with $n = 12$ (11) it is the widest. The broadening of the Soret band with larger n could most likely be explained by change of the host/guest complex rigidity. With shorter diamines such as 2, the host/guest complex is more rigid. In such cases, the decreased conformational flexibility would give rise to a narrower distribution of the excited state vibrational levels, thus the Soret band of the complex is sharper (shown schematically in Fig. 4b). In the case of longer diamines such as $n = 12$, the more flexible macrocyclic complex would lead to a wider conformational distribution, hence the Soret band is broader.

Fig. 5. Absorbance change of porphyrin tweezer 1 Soret band upon addition of diamine $n = 5$ (5). (For clarity, only spectra of selected concentration of diamines are shown).

The bathochromic shift of the porphyrin Soret band was accompanied with a clear isobestic point when tweezer 1 was titrated with diamines 2-11. Fig. 5 shows the change in absorbance upon addition of solution of diamine 5 to tweezer 1. The presence of the isobestic point suggests that the

TABLE 2—ASSOCIATION CONSTANTS (K_a) OF PORPHYRIN TWEEZER 1 WITH VARIOUS AMINES

Amine	K_a $\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$	Amine	K_a $\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$
$n = 2$ (2) ^a	2.6×10^7	$n = 8$ (8) ^a	2.2×10^8
$n = 3$ (3) ^a	3.8×10^8	$n = 9$ (9) ^a	1.7×10^8
$n = 4$ (4) ^a	1.0×10^8	$n = 10$ (10) ^a	2.0×10^7
$n = 5$ (5) ^a	4.5×10^8	$n = 12$ (11) ^a	3.0×10^6
$n = 6$ (6) ^a	2.4×10^8	Isopropyl-amine (12)	1.6×10^4 ($\text{dm}^6 \text{mol}^{-2}$)
$n = 7$ (7) ^a	2.8×10^8		

^a n denotes the number of methylene in diamine $\text{H}_2\text{N}(\text{CH}_2)_n\text{NH}_2$

adduct is a 1 : 1 host/guest complex. The calculated association constants (K_a) of the host/guest complexes (Table 2) show that there is only a limited degree of chain-length recognition of the diamine guests by tweezer 1. The relative constant values of K_a are not unexpected in view of the highly flexible structures of the host and guests. This means that tweezer 1 can accommodate different lengths of diamines ranging from $n = 2$ to 12 with almost similar affinities. The K_a values of complexes formed between the same series of diamines described here and the more rigid cage bisporphyrin molecule linked by two hexanediol ether linkers have been reported to be one to two orders of magnitude smaller than those reported here¹⁸. This is presumably due to the fact that tweezer 1 with the more flexible structure can give rise to a better fit between the host and guests.

In conclusion, the binding of flexible porphyrin host tweezer 1 and a series of acyclic α, ω -diamines shows that the bathochromic shift in λ_{max} and increase in $W_{1/2}$ of the Soret band of the host/guest complexes accompanying elongation of the guest chain-length can be ascribed to a decrease in exciton coupling and an increase in structural flexibility respectively.

Experimental

UV-vis spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer-Lambda 40 spectrophotometer. Anhydrous CH_2Cl_2 was dried over CaH_2 and distilled. Unless otherwise noted, materials were

obtained from commercial suppliers and were used without further purification.

For UV-vis measurements, a stock solution (0.1 mM) of porphyrin tweezer 1 in anhydrous CH₂Cl₂ was prepared. An aliquot of this stock solution (10 μL) was added to anhydrous CH₂Cl₂ to obtain 1 μM solution. Stock solutions (200 μM) of the diamines were prepared in anhydrous CH₂Cl₂. Aliquots of the diamine stock solution (1–50 μL) were added to the prepared porphyrin solution (0.2 eq to 10 eq). Stock solutions (20 and 200 mM) of isopropylamine were prepared in anhydrous CH₂Cl₂ and aliquots were added to the porphyrin solution (20 eq to 10000 eq). The porphyrin/amine solution was shaken and its uv-vis spectrum recorded at 298 K. All data were corrected by a dilution factor and background subtraction of the solvents. All ν_{\max} , λ_{\max} and half band-width of the host/diamine complexes were measured when binding to the host was saturated with 10 equivalent of guest diamines. Association constants were calculated from non-linear curve fitting analysis of 1 : 1 host-guest complexation.

Porphyrin tweezer 1 was synthesized as previously described¹³.

Acknowledgement

This work was supported by NIH grant GM 34509.

References

1. H. OGOSHI and T. MIZUTANI, *Acc. Chem. Res.*, 1998, **31**, 81.
2. C. A. HUNTER and J. K. M. SANDERS, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1990, **112**, 5525.
3. M. R. WASIELEWSKI, *Chem. Rev.*, 1992, **92**, 435.
4. H. IMAI, S. NAKAGAWA and E. KYUNO, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1992, **114**, 6719.
5. T. HAYASHI, M. NONOGUCHI, T. AYA and H. OGOSHI, *Tet. Lett.*, 1997, **38**, 1603.
6. M. J. CROSSLEY, L. G. MACKAY and A. C. TRY, *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Commun.*, 1995, 1925.
7. C. A. HUNTER, M. N. MEAH and J. K. M. SANDERS, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1990, **112**, 5773.
8. T. IMADA, H. MURAKAMI and S. SHINKAI, *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Commun.*, 1994, 1557.
9. K. KONISHI, K. YAHARA, H. TOSHISHIGE, T. AIDA and S. INOUE, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1994, **116**, 1337.
10. K. KONDO, Y. SHIOMI, M. SAISHO, T. HARADA and S. SHINKAI, *Tetrahedron*, 1992, **48**, 8239.
11. Y. KURODA, Y. KATO, T. HIGASHIOJI, J. HASEGAWA, K. KAWANAMI, M. TAKAHASHI, N. SHIRAISHI, K. TANABE and H. OGOSHI, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1995, **117**, 10950.
12. M. TAKEUCHI, T. IMADA and S. SHINKAI, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1996, **118**, 10658.
13. X. HUANG, B. H. RICKMAN, B. BORHAN, N. BEROVA and K. NAKANISHI, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1998, **120**, 6185.
14. S. MATILE, N. BEROVA, K. NAKANISHI, S. NOVKOVA, I. PHILIPOVA and B. BLAGOEV, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1995, **117**, 7021.
15. S. MATILE, N. BEROVA, K. NAKANISHI, J. FLEISCHHAUER and R. WOODY, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1996, **118**, 5198.
16. S. MATILE, N. BEROVA and K. NAKANISHI, *Enantiomer*, 1996, **1**, 1.
17. B. H. RICKMAN, S. MATILE, K. NAKANISHI and N. BEROVA, *Tetrahedron*, 1998, **54**, 5041.
18. I. P. DANKS, T. G. LANE, I. O. SUTHERLAND and M. YAP, *Tetrahedron*, 1992, **48**, 7679.
19. I. P. DANKS, I. O. SUTHERLAND and C. H. YAP, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 1*, 1990, 421.
20. M. KASHA, *Radiat. Res.*, 1963, **20**, 1059.
21. M. KASHA, H. R. RAWLS and M. A. EL-BAYOUMI, *Pure Appl. Chem.*, 1965, **11**, 371.
22. C. A. HUNTER, J. K. M. SANDERS and A. J. STONE, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1989, **133**, 395.